

The presence of green, immature, and husked grains (brown rice) was significantly higher in mechanically harvested rice than in hand-harvested and threshed rice for both varieties (see

table). The higher moisture percentage in the combine-harvested rice is due to the larger amount of green and immature grains, which may be attributed to the superior threshing efficiency of the

combine harvester. Total milling and head rice recovery in combine-harvested rice were 1.3-1.7 and 3.9-5.0% lower, respectively, than those in hand-harvested rice. □

Grain quality of some promising medium-grain rices

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We compared the physicochemical characteristics of some promising

medium-grain rice breeding lines with standard varieties IR6 and KS282. Rices were grown under similar environmental conditions in yield trials during 1988-90.

Eight of the 14 lines approached the standard varieties in kernel length and length-breadth ratio. Head rice recovery was 49.2-57.4% (see table). Only PK1385-9-1-B-1-1 gave slightly higher head rice than KS282. Broken rice

among lines tested was 14.0-20.0%. Proportionate elongation on cooking of eight lines was at par with that of IR6 and KS282. None of the lines approached KS282 in protein content. All lines, as well as the standard varieties, had high amylose content and low gelatinization temperature (alkali spreading value of 6-7). Gel consistency values ranged from 32 to 64 mm. □

Physicochemical characteristics of some promising medium-grain lines.

Variety or line	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	Length-breadth ratio	Milling recovery		Proportionate elongation on cooking	Protein content (%)	Amylose content (%)	Alkali spreading value	Gel consistency (mm)
				Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)					
PK1385-9-1-B-1-1	6.51	1.97	3.30	57.4	14.6	1.58	8.38	28.2	6.5	64
PK1385-9-1-B-1-12	6.51	1.95	3.34	55.7	14.0	1.63	9.00	28.2	6.4	47
PK1385-9-1-B-1-13	6.23	1.96	3.18	55.0	15.9	1.70	9.18	28.5	6.5	60
PK2480-7-3-1	6.62	1.76	3.76	55.3	16.0	1.70	8.38	29.5	6.5	47
PK3303-7-2	6.85	1.82	3.76	54.6	15.5	1.60	8.64	28.0	6.6	53
PK3305-15-1	6.84	1.81	3.78	53.5	17.2	1.61	8.73	28.5	6.5	56
PK3327-13-1	6.28	1.97	3.19	55.1	15.0	1.72	8.02	27.5	6.5	55
PK3358-13-3-2	6.47	1.84	3.52	54.0	16.6	1.75	8.38	29.5	6.5	47
PK3717-9	6.79	1.84	3.69	54.7	16.1	1.73	8.02	28.7	6.2	45
PK3717-12	6.75	1.85	3.65	53.0	17.3	1.75	8.46	28.0	6.5	42
PK3727-2	6.72	1.85	3.63	53.8	17.0	1.71	8.02	28.0	6.4	50
PK3721-5	6.74	1.87	3.60	56.0	15.2	1.65	8.28	28.5	6.5	47
PK3817-33	6.80	1.86	3.65	55.5	15.7	1.71	8.02	27.2	6.3	40
PK3849-18	6.81	1.82	3.74	49.2	20.0	1.64	8.12	28.0	6.5	32
IR6	6.72	1.84	3.65	55.7	15.2	1.70	7.62	29.1	6.6	41
KS282	6.84	1.79	3.82	57.0	14.6	1.74	9.87	28.3	6.5	46

Stress tolerance

Elite F₁ rice hybrids for low-light monsoon areas

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Low light is one of the major constraints to rice production during the wet season (WS). We compared tolerance for low light in selected F₁ rice hybrid combinations (Table 1) with the best low-light-tolerant standard check Swarnaprabha, during the 1990 WS and 1991 WS. The crop was grown in 1.2-m²

field plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing and fertilized with 60 kg N/ha.

Wooden screens were used to create low light (50% sunlight) conditions from 40 d after planting to harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 340 call cm² per d). The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. The two light treatments were in the main plots and the hybrids in the subplots. Leaf area index (LAI) at flowering, total dry matter (TDM), yield, and harvest index (HI) were recorded at harvest. The photosynthetic rate (P_n) of the boot

leaf at flowering was measured with the LI-6000 Portable Photosynthesis System at near saturated light (above 1,000 µE/m² per s).

P_n, crop photosynthesis (P_n × LAI), TDM, HI, and yield were consistently higher for the hybrids from the pollen parent Vajram, i.e., IR54752 A/Vajram during 1990 and from IR62829 A/Vajram during 1991. The yield, TDM, and HI were also the highest in these hybrids under low light. They were at par or even superior in yield to Swarnaprabha, especially under low light.

Hybrid IR62829 A/Vajram recorded the highest yield during the 1991 WS at

Table 1. Photosynthetic rate (P_n) at flowering, total dry matter (TDM), yield, and harvest index (HI) of F_1 rice hybrids under normal light and low light (50% normal) from 40d to harvest. Cuttack, India, 1990 and 1991 wet seasons.

Hybrid	Flowering		Harvest					
	P_n (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)	$P_n \times LAI$ (gCO ₂ /m ² per h)	TDM (g/m ²)		Yield (g/m ²)		HI (%)	
			Light	Shade	Light	Shade	Light	Shade
<i>1990 wet season</i>								
V20 A/Milyang 46	27.2	8.3	693	362	318	62	45	17
V20 A/IR36	31.1	8.4	634	346	209	102	33	29
IR54752 A/IR54	34.1	13.4	1201	483	413	159	34	33
IR54752 A/IR46	28.4	10.8	1115	497	343	83	31	17
IR54752 A/Vajram	36.1	14.3	1276	670	537	285	42	42
IR54752 A/Swarna	32.1	13.5	1041	393	345	73	33	18
Intan Mutant A/ARC11353	31.5	10.6	960	583	127	37	13	6
Intan Mutant A/IR27315	34.1	10.8	947	468	169	110	18	23
Swarnaprabha (check)	31.4	10.7	1146	619	537	231	47	37
Mean	31.8	11.2	1001	491	333	127	33	25
LSD (0.05)								
Hybrid (H)	2.1	1.2		23		25		—
Treatment (T)	—	—		54		41		—
H at same T	—	—		32		36		—
T at same H	—	—		48		36		—
<i>1991 wet season</i>								
IR62829 A/WGL	392543.7	11.3	794	181	383	29	49	16
IR62829 A/WGL	396232.0	9.1	817	274	434	84	53	30
IR62829 A/Swarna	42.0	17.4	1117	313	473	46	42	14
IR62829 A/Vajram	56.3	19.0	1187	448	536	140	45	31
IR62829 A/IR36	42.9	13.9	680	170	286	33	42	19
IR62829 Anellahamsa	47.6	11.6	811	286	345	55	43	18
Swarnaprabha	54.8	19.3	1167	481	567	142	49	28
Mean	45.6	14.5	939	308	432	76	46	22
LSD (0.05)								
Hybrid (H)	3.2	1.4		128		67		—
Treatment (T)	—	—		42		63		—
H at same T	—	—		181		94		—
T at same H	—	—		187		136		—

the Sugarcane Research Station, Vuyyuru, when it was grown after sugarcane in a well-drained fertile soil. Heterosis in yield over the pollen parent Vajram and standard heterosis over the best local check MTU 9992 were apparent (Table 2).

IR62829 A/Vajram, with 125-130 d total duration, was bred at Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, in the coastal monsoon belt of Andhra Pradesh, India. The hybrid has potential for use in the low-light monsoon areas. □

Table 2. Grain yield and heterosis in yield over the pollen parent of rice hybrids. Vuyyuru, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1991 WS.

Hybrid	Yield (g/m ²)	Heterosis over pollen parents
IR62829 A/WGL 3925	520	-9
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	442	-23
IR62829 A/Swarna	698	-11
IR62829 A/Vajram	831	19
IR62829 A/IR36	594	-2
IR62829 A/Tellahamsa	542	13
MTU9992 (check)	636	—
LSD (0.05)	120	

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Genetic variation of chlorophyll synthesis of etiolated Nepalese rice seedlings at low temperature: a new approach for cold tolerance screening

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Cold injury is a major constraint to improving rice production in the hills of Nepal because it limits both the rice-producing area and the growing season length. Many screening techniques for cold tolerance in rice at germination and early growth stages have been reported in the literature. We tested a new approach for cold tolerance screening by exposing etiolated leaf tissue of cold-sensitive

Comparative chlorophyll synthesis at 17°C among Nepalese indigenous and exotic rice genotypes.

Genotype	Field ranking ^a	Total chlorophyll (a+b) (µg)	Plumule color ^b (1-9 scale)
Sinjali	CT	0.151	1
Silange	CT	0.061	3
Chhomrong	CT (check)	0.061	3
Takmare	CT	0.048	3
China 1039	CT	0.037	3
Raksali	CT	0.033	3
Palung 2	CT	0.032	3
Bhatte	CT	0.025	5
IR20	CS	0.025	5
Seto Bhakunde	CT	0.024	5
Marshi	CS	0.021	5
Darmali	CT	0.019	7
Kalopatlle	CT	0.019	7
Juwari	CS	0.008	7
IR8	CS	0.002	9
IR36	CS (check)	0.001	9

r vs total chlorophyll content — -0.772**

^aCT = cold tolerant. CS = cold susceptible. ^bPlumule color (1 - 9 scale) 1 = dark green, 3 = light green, 5 = pale, 7 = tinge of greenness, and 9 = white.

species—including indicas—to low temperature (17°C). Within 24 h, the tissue shows variation in the rate of chlorophyll synthesis. The more cold-tolerant species are thus easily identified

Using the etiolated seedling approach we assessed 16 rice genotypes, including 10 indigenous cold-tolerant rices and 2 cold-susceptible rices for ability to synthesize chlorophyll at low temperature.

After breaking seed dormancy with heat treatment in a dry air oven at 50°C for 5 d, groups of 50 seeds were soaked in aerated distilled water for 24 h and placed in petri dishes on wet filter papers at 25°C for 3 d in the dark. They were then transferred—still in the dark—to 7°C for 24 h of acclimation followed by 48 h in a 10/14 h day/night cycle. We determined the extent of greening by spectrophotometrically measuring the total